

Amperometric Titrations of Praseodymium(III) and Neodymium(III) with Pyrocatechin Violet

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THE polarographic reduction of some sulphothalen dyes prompted us to make use of pyrocatechin violet (Abbrev. as PV) as an amperometric reagent. The dyes are referred in literature as spectrophotometric reagent¹. The present paper deals with the result of amperometric titration of titled metal ions with PV. The detailed polarography of PV and the effect of various experimental factors have been reported. The statistical data reveals the sensitivity of PV over others.

Experimental

The chemicals used were of AnalaR grade. Pr and Nd solutions were prepared by dissolving their oxide in the concentrated HCl and standardised². The polarography of PV was studied on a Toshniwal CLO-2B instrument. The capillary characteristic was $m^{3/2} t^{1/6} = 2.13 \text{ mg}^{2/3} \text{ s}^{1/2}$ at 40 cm effective height of mercury column. A Toshniwal CL-46 pH meter was used.

Procedure for amperometric titration: Sets of solution containing known amount of Nd and Pr in Britton-Robinson buffer at pH 5.0 ($\mu=0.4$) in 10 ml volume were prepared. The metal solution was taken in titration cell. Thermostated at 55°. Plateau potential on the wave of PV, i.e. -1.25 V vs Hg pool was applied. Standard solution of PV was then added to it and the current change noted³.

Results and Discussion

Polarograms of PV in Britton-Robinson buffer were taken at different concentrations. It gave single reduction wave at $\text{pH} \leq 4.5$ and two stage reduction wave at $\text{pH} \geq 4.6$. The half-wave potential for each of the steps was found to be shifted towards negative value. However, the observed limiting current was more or less pH independent. The dependence of the limiting current on the height of mercury column (h)^{1/2} at pH 5.0 shows linear dependence for $\log i - \log h$ plot (correlation coefficient, $r=0.998$). This proves that limiting current is proportional to the concentration of PV in the range 2.0×10^{-4} to $2.0 \times 10^{-3} M$ at pH 5.0. The $E_{1,2}$

values are -0.62 and -1.18 V vs Hg pool for the two daughter waves respectively. A slight positive shift in $E_{1,2}$ values was observed at higher temperature. This may be due to easier reduction and increase in degree of reversibility of the electrode process. Reproducible data were obtained at 55° using 0.5 M dye concentration.

In the amperometric titration, plots of currents vs volume revealed reverse L-shaped curve indicating stoichiometry of $1:1$ in each case. The results of determinations are presented in Table 1.

TABLE 1—AMPEROMETRIC TITRATION OF Pr^{III} AND Nd^{III} WITH PYROCATECHIN VIOLET*

pH=5.0, $\mu=0.4$, Plateau potential = -1.25 V vs Hg-pool.

Sl no.	Concn. M	Amount of metal (mg)		% Error
		Taken	Found	
1.	7×10^{-8}	0.097 2	0.097 8	+0.61
2.	8×10^{-6}	0.111 1	0.110 3	-0.72
3.	1×10^{-4}	0.138 9	0.138 0	-0.64
4.	2×10^{-4}	0.277 8	0.279 2	+0.50
5.	4×10^{-4}	0.555 6	0.551 2	-0.79
6.	6×10^{-4}	0.833 4	0.838 8	+0.64
7.	8×10^{-4}	1.111 2	1.102 6	-0.77
8.	1×10^{-3}	1.389 0	1.400 2	+0.80
9.	3×10^{-3}	4.167 0	4.143 8	-0.55

* Values calculated from replicate set of observation for each concentration

Amperometric titrations performed at room temperature ($\sim 25^\circ$) did not give reproducible results. This might be due to lower degree of dissociation

and higher degree of irreversibility at low temperature⁴. The optimum temperature chosen for these titrations is 55° as reproducible results were obtained for replicate set of titrations.

The known amount of foreign ions was added to definite amount of the metal ions and the proposed method was followed and the following ions (amount mg in parenthesis) did not interfere for both Nd and Pr: K^+ (98), Na^+ (69), Ca^{2+} (35), Mg^{2+} (33), Ba^{2+} (29) and Pb^{2+} (28.5); a 100-fold excess of chloride, chlorate, nitrate, acetate, iodide and sulphate had no effect. However, Ti^{4+} , Co^{2+} , Cu^{2+} , Ni^{2+} , Se^{4+} , Te^{4+} , Zn^{2+} , Cd^{2+} and other lanthanides interfered seriously.

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